

Sustainability and Recycling Pathways in Photovoltaic Energy Systems

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A thesis prepared as an independent research project in the
field of renewable energy engineering.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that this literature-based thesis is written as an independent researcher, based on literature analysis done by me. All the referred details have properly mentioned in the reference section. Even this is not done as a part of an academic program, all the writings have been done according to the post graduate writing standards of Liverpool John Moores University, England. All the contents of this report have not been submitted by me for any other university or institute for the award of any other programme.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ROSI - Recycling of Silicon from Solar Industry

EVA - Ethylene-Vinyl Acetate

C-Si - Crystalline Silicon

CdTe - Cadmium Telluride

CIGS - Copper Indian Gallium Selenide

EPBT - Energy Payback Time

FRELP - Full Recovery End of Life Photovoltaic

LGRF - Local Glass and Recovery Facility

LCA - Life Cycle Assessment

EROI - Energy Return On Investment

WEEE – Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment

EOL - End Of Life

TRL - Technology Readiness Levels

EPR - Extended Producer Responsibility

IEA - International Energy Agency

GHG - Greenhouse Gas

VOC - Volatile Organic Compound

DFR - Design For Recycling

PV - Photovoltaic

1 INTRODUCTION

The sun's radiation is the main source of life and energy which we experience on earth. It can be harness directly or as an indirect form like Coal and oil. When it comes to directly harnessing the sun energy to create electricity, solar photovoltaic technology plays a major role (Chen, et al., 2023) (Sark, et al., 2024). With the climate change and continuous development of the sustainable energy industry the Solar photovoltaic technology has become Increasingly popular among world energy generation and storage sector (Singh, et al., 2021) (Masson, et al., 2023). During a decade back since year 2022, from 104 to 1053 gigawatt increase in photovoltaic system installation have been seen and it is approximately 90% increment (Masson, et al., 2023) (solar power europe, 2025). In this development crystalline silicon Photovoltaic modules have demonstrated a major role by capturing Solar radiation to create electricity (Sark, et al., 2024) (Weckend, et al., 2016). Majority of the photovoltaic modules are depending on silicon technologies and these modules have approximate working period of less than 30 years (Australian government, 2025). researchers have predicted that approximately 2840 gigawatts of worldwide solar capacity will reach by 2030 and it will increase to 8650 gigawatts by 2050 (solar power europe, 2025) (Zobel, 2019). On the other hand, with around 30-year life span of photovoltaic modules, by 2050 it has been predicted to get nearly 78 million ton of solar panel waste (ROSI, 2025) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Also, it has been created several waste management Challenges due to requirement of processing various type of solar panels at the end of the life of solar panels (NREL, 2025) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). However with the continuous improvement of the photovoltaic technology, older models will Get replaced with new photovoltaic modules before the end of the life and due to this reason it is assumed to get more than 78 million tons of solar panel waste by 2050 (Fu, et al., 2018) (OECD, 2016).

Most of the photovoltaic systems available today are not planned to go through recycling process and that have become increasing environmental concern, therefore it has been identified that introducing recycling steps to currently available “take-make-use-dispose” linear model is essential to go toward sustainable and circular industry (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). It has been identified that, this help to decrease the extensive usage of natural resources while gaining higher financial benefits (Preet & Smith,

2024). when moving towards recycling of photovoltaic systems it is crucial to identify the most effective method to use on different steps (nature, 2025).

Figure 1.1 Global photovoltaic growth

Linear model of “take-make-use-dispose” have various end of life risks associated with it and Australia can be name as one of the countries that have analyzed this properly (Franco & Groesser, 2021). After near 30-year lifetime of photovoltaic modules, it has been identified three crucial situations to consider as, 1) disposal to landfills 2) recycling by Limited glass recycling facilities 3) recycling by full recovery of end-of-life photovoltaics (nature, 2025). Disposing photovoltaic module to landfills have been Identified as the most common out of above three situations while other to have considerable benefits. With the previous research, it has been proven that, by adhering to “Recycling by laminated glass recycling facility” or “Recycling by full recovery of end-of-life photovoltaics” scenarios, overall impact score of the cradle to Grave can be reduce from 0.00706 to 0.00657 and 0.00523 respectively, under the life cycle assessment “ReCiPe endpoint single score” (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Deng, et al., 2019). Also, in compared to “disposal to landfills” scenario, carbon dioxide emission to the environment gets reduced from 0.059kgperkwh to 0.054kgperkwh in “recycling by laminated glass recycling facility” and to 0.046kgperkwh in “recycling by full recovery of end-of-life photovoltaics” scenarios (PV Magazine, 2025). Furthermore, it is proven that by improving the lifetime of the photovoltaic module more than 30 years, negative impacts to the environment

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can be reduced (Hund, et al., 2020). However, when considering the Environmental impact of the photovoltaic module recycling, data related to the building recycling plants is difficult to find due to the lack of existing new recycling plants (European Commission, 2025). When photovoltaic recycling plant construction details were added to the environment impact scale, above mentioned scores are susceptible to vary and therefore the most effective method of reducing natural resources and environmental impact is improving the life span of the photovoltaic modules (Ribo, et al., 2023).

At the end of the nearly 30-year lifetime of the photovoltaic modules, most of them have ended up as waste. In countries like Australia, Photovoltaic waste is also considered as electronic waste and they are ended up in landfills or incineration plants (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (European Commission, 2025). There have been clearly identified risks related to incineration as burning electronic waste releases toxic and carcinogenic compounds to the surrounding environment and atmosphere (Ribo, et al., 2023). It has been identified that photovoltaic waste will reach nearly 10% out of total generated electrical and electronic waste by 2050 and when it comes to Australia, it has been estimated 800000 Tons of photovoltaic waste by 2047 (Science, 2025). Furthermore, when moving towards a circular economy while mitigating the harmful effect of the photovoltaic industry, it is crucial to consider end of life management practices in every stage of the photovoltaic system such as design, production, operation and decommissioning.

According to the researchers, it has been identified that areas such as 1) Waste management practices 2) Human health 3) Natural environment 4) Water source specificity 5) Economic performance, are the most impacted sectors by the Solar photovoltaic industry (Peng, et al., 2012). When it comes to rooftop photovoltaic systems, Australia has been identified as the country with the fastest adapting households in the world (Masson, et al., 2023). Yet the end of the life cycle management of the photovoltaic systems remains as an under-discussed issue in Australia (Franco & Groesser, 2021). Moreover, raw material extraction and processing of photovoltaic component, transportation and manufacturing, balance of system components, manufacturing, photovoltaic system installation and operation decommissioning or recycling processes of the photovoltaic system at the end of their lifetime have been identified as the main steps of the life cycle process of solar photovoltaic system (European Commission, 2021) (Zobel, 2019). It has been identified that circular Business models are capable of Stimulating smart component Design, resource efficiency, value capture and product reuse from the waste (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). Unfortunately,

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with the effort of creating recyclable Photovoltaic panels with high levels of efficiency has led to reuse of old photovoltaic panels which is costly (Preet & Smith, 2024). To obtain stability through strong connections Which are braced by coevolving policies, technology readiness, market infrastructure, user practices and cultural meaning, Multi level perspective state that, Technology changes should happen on socio-technical system Over period of time (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Hund, et al., 2020).

The main objective of this research is to evaluate sustainability and recycling methods of photovoltaic systems in the angle of life cycle analysis. Furthermore, this research focuses on determining how various recycling technologies help to achieve circular economy goals while mitigating environmental impacts. For the purpose of achieving them, this research goes through several key points that give an overall explanation on sustainability of the photovoltaic system. As the first step, crucial stages of the photovoltaic life cycle such as material extraction, manufacturing, installation, operation and end of life management, have been explained while considering Important environment indicators like energy return on investment, Greenhouse gas emission and energy payback time. Secondly, a comparative analysis towards main recycling technologies such as mechanical, thermal, chemical and hybrid methods have been done while considering their technological maturity, economic feasibility and material recovery efficiency. As the third step, the research explores regulatory frameworks that apply to photovoltaic waste management under the emphasis on global models such as the European Union waste electrical and electronic equipment directive and their applicability in Australia. Moreover, in this research a conceptual framework has been developed which consists of recycling pathways, various policies and sustainability matrices which motivates the circular photovoltaic industry. In the end, this research points out a major gap in policies and research that are present, while suggesting a strategic method to improve high value recycling that implements circularity principles which guide the photovoltaic industry in the direction of an efficient and sustainable future.

2.1 Introduction to life cycle

When it comes to the life cycle of the photovoltaic system, Cradle to Grave analysis such as Mining for materials to end of the life recycling steps are there. It has been identified that to assess environmental foot print of photovoltaic technology and to improve the sustainability, life cycle analysis is an essential step. Every stage of life cycle of the photovoltaic system affect differently to scenario slide energy emissions and resource consumption. For the analysis of recycling method and circular system designs, it is essential to have a strong knowledge on the complete life cycle of the photovoltaic system.

2.2 Detailed life cycle phases**2.2.1 Raw material acquisition**

Raw material acquisition has been identified as the very first step of the life cycle of photovoltaic system. When considering the total environmental performance of the photovoltaic technology, raw material acquisition has significant influence on it (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024). Quartz sand is the source of high purity silicon which is the Basic material used in crystalline Silicon photovoltaic modules that dominate the Global production (Singh, et al., 2021) (Zobel, 2019). Heavy amounts of electrical energy and thermal energy is required for the transformation process of metallurgical grade silicon to solar-grade silicon. This stage has been identified as the most energy intensive step in photovoltaic life cycle and it often achieves this energy through fossil fuels (Peng, et al., 2012) (Weckend, et al., 2016).

Besides of silicon there are other Important materials are used in photovoltaic module, such as glass for encapsulation, trace metals such as silver, copper, tin and lead for the purpose of electrical connection, glass for the encapsulation, aluminum for the frames and Ethylene-vinyl acetate for lamination (Australian PV Institute, 2023). However high embodied emissions, land degradation and water contamination have been identified as the major concerns that arise during mining and refining of these materials (solar power europe, 2025). More over because of the supply risk and scarcity of materials such as indium and silver they have been categorized as critical raw materials (United Nations Environment Programme,

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2007) (European Commission, 2025). Therefore, It is essential to minimize the dependency on virgin resources as this highlights the sustainability challenges in the long run and underlines the importance of circular sourcing strategies, material substitution and recycling (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (European Commission, 2021).

2.2.2 Module manufacturing

In a photovoltaic life cycle the one of the most energy and resource intensive stages have been identified as photovoltaic module manufacturing (Fan, et al., 2024) (Singh, et al., 2021). Manufacturing process of crystalline Silicon modules Initiate with Purified solar Grade Silicon melting and casting into ingots Followed by slicing process using wire saws (Zobel, 2019). Furthermore, With the assistance of high priority chemicals, clean room environment and precise thermal treatment, the next immediate steps of Module manufacturing were performed and all these steps such as doping, surface texturing, anti reflective coating and metallization, required a high amount of energy (Weckend, et al., 2016). When it comes to the photovoltaic module assembly stage, it goes through encapsulating the cells within a layer of glass and Ethylene-vinyl acetate, Attachment of back sheet, junction box integration and finally aluminum framing (Chen, et al., 2023) (Peng, et al., 2012). This process contributes to most of the consumed carbon in photovoltaic system (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Consumption of the high cost and rare material such as silver which is used for front contact of the photovoltaic module, considered as the material which has a considerable footprint toward environment impact (solar power europe, 2025) (European Commission, 2025). However, novel methods and technologies of improving sustainability and reducing emission of the module manufacturing stage, such as Renewable energy integration into the manufacturing facilities, improvement in material efficiency and low temperature processing, have been popular these days (Biyouki, et al., 2024).

2.2.3 System installation

System installation is the immediate step after the module manufacturing, so that it can be integrated into a functional energy system (Franco & Groesser, 2021). In this step not only the photovoltaic modules, all the other components and processes related to photovoltaic energy generation and storage systems such as fixing Photovoltaic modules on mounting structure,

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installing electrical protection systems, cabling, inverter installation and the installation of energy storage equipment were carried out (Australian PV Institute, 2023). In comparison to the module manufacturing process, the environmental footprint of the installation is minimal. However, this environmental impact has been identified as a varying factor due to Correlated processes such as transportation, use of construction materials and the land use (Weckend, et al., 2016). During site preparation for utility scale ground Mounted photovoltaic system installation, soil erosion and local ecosystems gets disrupted as a result of land Clearing and grading (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). Even though with challenges like structural compatibility and availability of labor, rooftop photovoltaic systems have been identified as a good solution for this. When considering the sustainability performance of the photovoltaic module life cycle design decisions that have been made during the installation process like shading orientation and inclination have considerable impact on photovoltaic systems energy output in the long run (Fan, et al., 2024) (Peng, et al., 2012).

2.2.4 Operational use phase

The General Lifespan of a photovoltaic system is considered between 25 to 30 years (Singh, et al., 2021). This is the phase of the photovoltaic life cycle where it pays back for the energy and environment costs that occurred during the manufacturing process. One of the key parameter that is used to evaluate this, is Energy Payback Time(EPBT) and it shows the time required for the system to produce the equal amount of energy that has been used to create it (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Peng, et al., 2012). When considering the crystalline Silicon photovoltaic module, energy payback time is in between 1 to 3 years and this may vary depending on photovoltaic technology, system configuration and the location (Fan, et al., 2024) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Similarly, energy return on investment also can be obtained nearly 10:1 value during this phase, while proving promising sustainability performance. Furthermore, with very low amount of module efficiency degradation percentage Which is around 0.5% to 0.8%, photovoltaic module can be operated for several decades with economical levels of operation (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (solar power europe, 2025). This performance can be developed with inverter replacement, regular maintenance and infrastructure monitoring (Biyouki, et al., 2024).

2.2.5 End of life management

By 2050 with the current photo politic deployment and growth, the amount of end of life modules predicted to reach nearly 78 million tons and this require immediate sustainable waste management practices (Chen, et al., 2023) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). In most areas that lack recycling infrastructure and regulatory framework, the most frequent end of life method is land filling (Franco & Groesser, 2021). Furthermore, there are environmental risks attached with the land filling method as it releases toxic material such as tin, lead to the soil and precious metals such as silver may be lost permanently (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). Currently there are limited material recovery methods present, such as basic mechanical recycling, which is done by manual dismantling and shredding to recover Glass and Aluminum (Fan, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019). However there have been some energy intensive and commercially limited Processes are available to recover valuable compounds such as Silicon wafer and silver, named thermal treatment and chemical etching (solar power europe, 2025). Therefore, novel end of life methods have been identified as a necessary factor for the circular economy model of photovoltaic systems, so that it helps to reintegrate recovered material into the manufacturing process while minimizing the photovoltaic waste (European Commission, 2021) (Australian PV Institute, 2023).

Figure 2.1 Photovoltaic waste projection

2.3 Sustainability Matrices in photovoltaics

A quantitative metric that captures environmental impact and energy efficiency is required to analyze the sustainability of a photovoltaic system during the life cycle (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024). Energy payback time (EPBT) has been identified as the most commonly used indicator for this purpose (Peng, et al., 2012) (Weckend, et al., 2016). Also the ratio of total energy output to energy input over the system lifespan, which is known as energy return on investment(EROI) is very similar to EPBT (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (Singh, et al., 2021). For novel systems, energy return on investment value goes more than 10:1 demonstrating higher benefit for net energy (Zobel, 2019). Greenhouse gas emission has been identified as another key parameter which has units of gCO_{2-eq}/kWh for lifetime of the system and for the Silicon, best photovoltaic module got value which varies from 20 to 60 as shown in the life cycle assessment(LCA) (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (Franco & Groesser, 2021). In comparison to fossil fuel related energies this value is considerably low. Through all these parameters, it has been proven that photovoltaic systems are energy positive low emission Technology (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

2.3.1 Life cycle assessment findings from Australian content

By considering the features like transportation, electricity mix and waste handling, life cycle assessment is capable of giving details distinct to the location, regarding environment performance of a photovoltaic system (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024). With respect to the end-of-life practices used, it has been shown that in countries like Australia where Rapid growth in photovoltaic industry is present, life cycle assessment shows considerable changes in emission of greenhouse gases. Based on a study that have been conducted related to 3 end of life practices which are landfilling, local glass and recovery facility pathway and full recovery end of life photography process, landfilling have identified as the worst method that create high environment destruction by releasing $25gCO_{2-eq}/kWh$ through the Photovoltaic module lifespan (Singh, et al., 2021). Therefore, by moving towards local glass and recovery facility(LGRF) pathway and full recovery end of life photovoltaic(FRELP) processes, significant amount of greenhouse gas emission can be reduced as it recovers materials like Silicon aluminum and glass from the old modules (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (Zobel, 2019). With the proof of the various research, it has been found that sustainability metrics

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depend on various factors such as technology, recycling infrastructure, regional waste policy and system boundaries (solar power europe, 2025). Furthermore, by applying circular economic principles into photovoltaic systems, emission and energy performance can be improved at a system level (European Commission, 2021).

Figure 2.2 Scenario Comparison (Landfill vs. Glass Recycling vs. Full Recovery)

2.3.2 Technology comparisons and sustainability trade-offs

As mentioned before sustainability Matrix depends on various factors (Franco & Groesser, 2021). Even though technologies with lower energy input in manufacturing processes with short energy payback time (EPBT), less than 1.5 years exist, such as Copper Indium Gallium Selenide (CIGS) and Cadmium Telluride (CdTe), the most commonly used module technology is Crystalline Silicon (C-Si) (Peng, et al., 2012) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). The downside of above-mentioned thin film technologies is the use of toxic and rare material such as Cadmium and Tellurium (European Commission, 2025) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). When considering the Crystalline Silicon modules, it is a relatively common material with considerable durability, many methods for recycling and the only flow in this technology is that intensive energy use in the production process (Singh, et al., 2021). Environmental footprint of crystalline silicon technology has been able to reduce further with the improvements of the bifacial technology, high throughput manufacturing and cell efficiency (solar power europe, 2025). Therefore, it is clear that with the combination of system design,

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end of life treatment, material choice and energy mix, sustainability of the photovoltaic system gets determined. They are crucial for the future sustainable and circular Energy Transition (Biyouki, et al., 2024).

2.4 Photovoltaic recycling Technologies

2.4.1 *Mechanical thermal and chemical recycling methods*

Photovoltaic module recycling consists of several steps procedure with intentions of recovery in precious materials and mitigation of environmental impacts (Chen, et al., 2023). Presently there are three major methods of recycling as mechanical, chemical and thermal with specific advantages and boundaries (Fan, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019). Out of these three mechanical recycling is the oldest and most common recycling method. In mechanical recycling it has to go through manual dismantling, threading and density base separation processes for the purpose of extracting components such as junction boxes, glass and aluminum frames (Franco & Groesser, 2021). Even though the mechanical recycling process is economically beneficial, it is unable to extract materials like silver contact and silicon wafer, because of encapsulation in polymers (Peng, et al., 2012). Thermal recycling Method can be identified as a solution for this problem, as it uses control pyrolysis at temperatures around 600 to 700 Celsius for the purpose of decomposing Ethylene-Vinyl Acetate (EVA) layer, so that mechanical or chemical recycling steps can be carried out (Australian PV Institute, 2023). There are several disadvantages attached to this process, as it only recovers silicon and other metals partially and this process consumes high amount of energy while releasing toxic gases (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). The third and final method is chemical recycling and it is still in the laboratory testing stage due to its safety, scalability and waste management challenges (Singh, et al., 2021). However, it is by far the most successful recycling method as it dissolves encapsulants and enables the extraction of materials like silver, tin, lead and solar-grade silicon separately with the help of solvents, acids or alkaline solutions (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025).

2.4.2 Advanced recycling/High-Purity material recovery and ROSI process

To extract high value material such as indium, solar grade silicon and silver, while avoiding the boundaries of conventional methods of recycling, advanced photovoltaic recycling technologies have appeared (solar power europe, 2025) (Zobel, 2019). When considering the recent advanced recycling methods, Recycling of Silicon from Solar Industry (ROSI) can be identified as one of the most successful methods in recovering nearly 98% of high purity silicon and 95% of silver using a combination of chemical separation, non-destructive delamination and thermal treatment (Biyouki, et al., 2024). As the ROSI method consumes a low amount of energy and operates in low temperature conditions, recovered materials don't go through thermal degradation (Australian PV Institute, 2023). As this allows to collect intact silicon wafer for reuse, considerable cost reduction and circularity can be achieved. However, there are some boundaries in ROSI process such as high operation cost, Limited regulatory drivers and that is the main reason for it still not being fully commercialized (Peng, et al., 2012). Moreover, there are some alternate advanced recycling methods such as supercritical fluid extraction and selective leaching for certain metals, however these methods are still in experimental state (Fan, et al., 2024). Furthermore, for the purpose of overcoming bulk recovery while moving towards closed loop photovoltaic recycling systems, it is essential to blend with novel high efficiency recycling techniques (Franco & Groesser, 2021).

2.4.3 Global status and implementation challenges

Because of considerable fluctuations in infrastructure readiness, technological adaptation and policy enforcements, photovoltaic recycling keeps improving worldwide (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (Chen, et al., 2023). With the help of waste from, electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) directive have been able to make manufacturers accountable for the photovoltaic waste and have encouraged them to move towards developments in recycling technologies within the European Union (solar power europe, 2025). Even though France and Germany are still dependent on basic mechanical processors for cycling, because of constraints such as regulatory framework and economic reasons, they have been able to launch several advanced recycling plants in prototype level (Zobel, 2019) (Peng, et al., 2012). However, most of the countries in other parts of the world except Europe, does not have successful end of life(EOL) frameworks and therefore most of the photovoltaic waste end up in landfills (Franco

Sustainability and Recycling Pathways in Photovoltaic Energy Systems & Groesser, 2021) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). One of the major reasons for lack of recycling practices in these countries is due to very low value of recovered material they get from older modules that have very minimum amount of silver and other valuable materials, compared to cost of recycling process (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Furthermore, most of the recycling plants present in these countries remain in a lower level of Technology Readiness levels (TRL) around 5 to 7 for implementing in to industry (Fan, et al., 2024). In addition, when planning the photovoltaic module design there should be a recycling map for that certain model, called design for disassembly and unfortunately that also does not happen most of the time (Singh, et al., 2021). For the purpose of enabling circularity and high efficiency recycling, into the worldwide Photovoltaic industries, all the above-mentioned limitations have to be overcome through technological development, policy changes and market incentives (Biyouki, et al., 2024).

2.5 Policy and regulatory context

2.5.1 Extended producer responsibility and European regulations

For this sole purpose of addressing predicted high amounts of photovoltaic waste at the end of life of currently available systems, the European Union added some changes to waste electrical and electronic equipment(WEEE) directive in 2012 so that it specifically applies to photovoltaic panels (solar power europe, 2025) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). This is known as extended producer responsibility (EPR) and under this regulation, photovoltaic module producers are responsible to spend money on collecting, treating and recycling the photovoltaic modules that are sold in the European region (Zobel, 2019). Under the influence of this directive, institutions like “PV Cycle” have been established and they have been able to manage recycling and logistic facilities of affiliate countries (Peng, et al., 2012) (solar power europe, 2025). Also, this directive forces photovoltaic module manufacturing companies to collect at least 85% and recycle at least 80% of waste according to their weight (European Commission, 2021). Even though there is progress when managing the infrastructure investments, due to fluctuations in financial techniques and national enforcements, it is problematic to deploy them evenly in every region (Franco & Groesser, 2021). However, the extended producer responsibility (EPR) approach remains as a guideline of photovoltaic waste management rules and encourage the

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improvement of more advanced techniques of recycling in the industry (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

2.5.2 Australian policy landscape and gaps

Australia can be identified as a country that is transitioning towards the photovoltaic industry due to government influence and high amount of solar radiation availability, therefore practices in managing photovoltaic waste at the end of life are continuously changing (Singh, et al., 2021). In Australia there are no specific EPR directive for photovoltaic waste like in Europe, however there are continuous discussions on this topic (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Unfortunately, in Australia most of the photovoltaic modules that reach the end of life, go to landfills or go through Unregulated recycling practices (Fan, et al., 2024). Few of the main reasons for this discontinuous recycling methods were absence of collection infrastructure, good procedures and financial support (Zobel, 2019). Therefore, priority under the products stewardship act was produced for the purpose of creating a recycling scheme at National level in 2021 by the Australian government (Australian government, 2025). This has been able to create several positive impacts Such as banning, sending electronic waste to landfills in Victoria state (Franco & Groesser, 2021). However, to successfully move towards circular economy, Australia need to implement further advanced Extended producer responsibility (EPR) methods with help of Government as well as private sector contribution (Biyouki, et al., 2024).

2.5.3 Global initiatives and International Energy Agency (IEA) guidance

Apart from the directives made by countries individually, due to developing problems related photovoltaic waste, international organizations have made their concern toward this industry (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). One of such organizations is the International Energy agency (IEA) and it has been given Policy recommendation and technical guidelines through their photovoltaic power system program for sustainable Photovoltaics waste management practices (Chen, et al., 2023). Under these practices, they are promoting international collaboration on best practices, promoting designs based on life cycle, data collection on Photovoltaic waste flows standardization (solar power europe, 2025). The International Energy Agency has highlighted the importance of “design for recyclability” which allows manufacturers to consider ways of end-of-life material recovery at

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the module development step (Zobel, 2019). Even though due to limitations in industry, motivation and regulatory enforcement, absorbing these practices into the industry remains a challenge (Peng, et al., 2012). As photovoltaic technology still remains new in most of the countries, their waste is considered as common electronic waste and therefore recovering the materials have become a challenge (Franco & Groesser, 2021). When it comes to developing countries, the lack of end-of-life practices of photovoltaic modules have resulted them being exported as second hand electronics or to an unacceptable disposing method. Therefore, it is essential to conduct Research and building infrastructure, while introducing new policies to achieve circular economy target that synchronize regulatory approaches to mitigate growing worldwide end of life photovoltaic waste crisis (European Commission, 2021).

2.6 Gaps in Literature

2.6.1 Design weaknesses and limited circularity

Even though, a considerable amount of photovoltaic module recycling research is available, still there is a certain amount of mismatching is present to reach circular economical goals (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024). Shortage of disassemble friendly photovoltaic module design have been identified as one of the major issues, as with thermally cross-linked encapsulants like EVA, end of life material recovery has become economically and energetically expensive (Zobel, 2019). Due to that, during the recycling process valuable material such as silver and silicon wafer remains in unrecoverable condition (Franco & Groesser, 2021). This has been a result of less collaboration between manufacturers and recyclers at the design stage and it's a major obstacle for close loop material recovery (Peng, et al., 2012). Furthermore, currently available research is mainly focusing on performance and cost effectiveness rather than end of life practices, therefore creating a recycling friendly module architecture has become a challenge (Singh, et al., 2021). From the industrial perspective, until the proper industrial policies and motivation towards circular designs are introduced, end of life recycling will always not become a major concern (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Finally, this design gap between manufacturers and recyclers will increase the recycling cost, while reducing the opportunities for Low impact recyclable technologies (solar power europe, 2025).

2.6.2 Data deficiencies and technology readiness gaps

Data deficiency related to large scale performance of photovoltaic recycling systems have been identified as a major issue related to existing research (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024). The majority of currently available recovery efficiency models and life cycle assessments are primarily based on laboratory experiment or simulation and therefore it has been difficult to relate them to industrial level full scale recycling (Weckend, et al., 2016). Therefore, most of the recovery rate related to material such as solar grade silicon or silver are just predictions which have not proven completely (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (Zobel, 2019). Furthermore, in the technology readiness level, presently available free cycling methods stand in between range of 5 to 7 and that means they are still on demonstration level (Peng, et al., 2012). Even though there are a small number of recycling facilities that operate in industrial capacity, they are highly dependent on policy mandates and subsidies (solar power europe, 2025). Moreover, there is a Deficit in Research related to economic viability studies which contains details on methods of declining material cost of latest photovoltaic modules by reducing the content of expensive material such as silver. This causes challenges in investment appeal and scalability related to photovoltaic recycling methods. For the purpose of connecting research to industry, it is essential to have further policy driven funding models, field data and longitudinal performance matrices (Singh, et al., 2021).

2.6.3 Economic and policy limitations in research

Economic feasibility and environmental performance in photovoltaic recycling have been identified as another area which lacks proper research (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (Fan, et al., 2024). Rather than considering comprehensive cost benefit analysis related to transportation, labor, regulatory compliance and processing, most of the currently available research is based on usage of energy and material recovery (Weckend, et al., 2016) (solar power europe, 2025). As an example, methods with high efficiency, such as high-purity or chemical recovery are not effective without solid financial background and supportive policies (Zobel, 2019). In addition, there can be found some research related to volatile market value of recovered material that explain their effect on investment viability and profitability (Peng, et al., 2012). When considering the environmental effects, most of the research that is available today focuses on reduction of emission rather than considering other serious effects such as local ecosystem risks,

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safety of the laborers and hazardous byproduct handling that generate through the residues of recycling (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). When considering the supervisory section of recycling, there are very few research available regarding, how outdated research can affect innovative recycling methods (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (European Commission, 2021). These differences make it difficult to create scalable and realistic future plans for photovoltaic waste management. However, by making collaborations between areas such as Environmental Sciences, policy analysis and economics, more futuristic photovoltaic waste management plan can be generated (Australian PV Institute, 2023).

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research approach

Based on secondary data analysis, this research follows a qualitative research approach. With the help of already available publications, such as policy document and technical reports on photovoltaic energy system related recycling and sustainability Pathways, a comprehensive interpretation, synthesis and comparison have been done in this research. Due to that, a strong analysis on end-of-life management strategies, recycling technology and photovoltaic life cycle sustainability have been able to be done.

Figure 3.1 Photovoltaic life cycle process

While keeping sustainability matrices like Greenhouse gas (GHG) emission, energy payback time (EPBT) and energy return on investment (EROI) as comparison parameter, an analysis on basic stages of photovoltaic system’s life cycle such as acquisition of materials, module manufacturing, installation, operation and end of life management have been done throughout this research. Similarly, according to their economic feasibility, maturity of technology and

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However, rather than creating new experiment data, this research helps to connect existing knowledge by eliminating gaps and identifying future research potential with the help of recommendations based on evidence, comparative analysis and conceptual models.

3.2 Data sources

Based on several sources, this analysis has been done and the reason for choosing those documents can be mentioned as, direct reliability to sustainability and recycling of photovoltaic systems, technical depth and credibility of Peer reviews. Under this documentation list there are several journal articles, reports, websites and one text book under the topic of “Photovoltaic Solar Energy: From Fundamentals to Application Volume 2” (Sark, et al., 2024). All the academic document that has been used here are properly referenced.

Out of above-mentioned documentations, the textbook has been used as the main source of technical reference to cover the topics of sustainability matrix, recycling Technologies and life cycle of photovoltaic systems. The remaining journal articles, reports, websites have been used as source of case studies and latest findings.

These journal articles, reports and websites have been able to provide comprehensive details on technical performance, regulating policies and latest industry practices. With the combination of the textbook, journal articles, reports and websites It has been possible to analyze the available data, while mitigating the risk of bias through the triangulation approach.

3.3 Evaluation framework

For the purpose of rating the recycling effectiveness and sustainability performance of a photovoltaic system with the help of published documents, an evaluation framework has been

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created. Policy alignment, technical performance and environment impact have been identified as the basic parameters that are supportive in this analysis.

With comparison of recycling Pathways such as advanced hybrid, thermal, mechanical and chemical processes with respect to technology readiness level(TRL), requirements of process energy, rate of material recovery and complexity of the operations, technical performance have been analyzed (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Zobel, 2019) (ROSI, 2025) (Fu, et al., 2018) (Deng, et al., 2019).

When it comes to evaluation of environmental impacts, It is carried out mainly with the help of life cycle analysis, however other factors such as greenhouse gas(GHG) emission, energy payback time(EPBT) and energy return on investment are also considered (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Preet & Smith, 2024) (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (Peng, et al., 2012).

The level of adherence of technology development and recycling practices to regulatory frameworks, such as recommendations of International Energy agency(IEA) (Masson, et al., 2023) (Australian PV Institute, 2023), directives of European waste electrical and electronic equipment (WEEE) (European Commission, 2021) and Australia's emerging product stewardship approach (Australian government, 2025) are inspected by the policy alignment. In the policy alignment, it checks not only the present adherence but also the absorption capabilities towards upcoming political changes.

While giving an opportunity to identify the most suitable recycling method according to geographical limitation and official directives, above mentioned three parameters help to conduct multi criteria analysis. Also, by connecting policy and environment objectives with technical capabilities this multi criteria analysis help to build a conceptual model for circular Photovoltaic deployment.

3.4 Conceptual framework development

When integrating policy considerations, sustainability metrics and recycling Pathways towards collected circular photovoltaic system design, this conceptual framework assists as an analytical and visual model. By comparing and plotting the details in journal articles (Chen, et al., 2023) (Singh, et al., 2021) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024) and the textbook (Sark, et al., 2024) against the basic stages of the photovoltaic life cycle which are acquisition of raw materials, manufacturing of photovoltaic modules, installation, operation and management of the end of life, this process has been done.

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In the middle of this diagram a feedback loop can be found which represents the collected materials at the recycling process that recontributes to the manufacturing of photovoltaic modules while reducing the extraction of natural resources and environmental impacts (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Fu, et al., 2018) (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Deng, et al., 2019). Within this framework, placement of each recycling path is done by the technical data related to technology readiness level, recovery efficiency and energy inputs. Furthermore, the order of the importance of each path is calculated by the sustainability indicators like Greenhouse gas emissions, energy payback time and energy return on investment (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Preet & Smith, 2024) (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (Peng, et al., 2012).

Moreover, for the purpose of strengthening the clarity, a policy layer is included in this framework, with regulatory mechanisms such as eco designs standards, extended producer responsibilities schemes and landfill bans (OECD, 2016). With these methods This Framework can illustrate practical feasibility and alignment of the governance.

While giving an opportunity to the interested parties to get an idea on the interconnection between policy support technology and sustainable performance, the final structure works as a communication aid and analytical tool. With above mentioned measurements the framework is able to identify the critical points which can transfer the linear model into a circular photovoltaic model.

Figure 3.2 Circular economy vs linear model

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Using a 'Graphviz dot' code, the below shown conceptual model has been obtained.

Figure 3.3 Conceptual model

For the purpose of comfortable reading, it is recommended to run the 'Graphviz code' mentioned in appendix, using below shown link and download a picture of the conceptual design.

<https://dreampuf.github.io/GraphvizOnline/?engine=dot#digraph%20G%20%7B%0A%0A%20%20%0A%7D> (Graphviz, 2025).

3.5 Data analysis method

Date analysis method is done as a structured method, which involves interpreting data after extracting and organizing them from above mentioned academic documents. As the first step systematic content analysis is carried out. At this stage every source is checked to identify details related to photovoltaic policy framework, recycling technologies, lifecycle stages and sustainability matrices (Sark, et al., 2024) (Chen, et al., 2023) (Singh, et al., 2021) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024) (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Fu, et al., 2018) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Deng, et al., 2019). After that, gathered details were grouped according to the topic relativity, to the literature review.

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As the second step, technical variables of recycling pathway like technology readiness level, rate of recovery for silicon glass, process energy consumption and precious metal, were summarized with the help of comparative tables (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Zobel, 2019) (ROSI, 2025) (Fu, et al., 2018) (Deng, et al., 2019). Cross referencing method is followed to find continuities and discontinuities in the situations of the same metric which is reported by several sources. This help to find out most common and uncommon scenarios in the dataset.

For the purpose of evaluating comparative weakness and strengths in every recycling pathway, multi-criteria analysis in combination with policy alignment, technical performance and environmental indicator were used in the third state (European Commission, 2021) (Australian government, 2025) (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (OECD, 2016). As this data can be considered as secondary, for the benchmarks like Greenhouse gas emission, energy payback time and energy return on investment, It has been realized that qualitative analysis is more suitable compared to recalculation (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Preet & Smith, 2024) (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (Peng, et al., 2012).

Finally, the gathered perceptions are combined so that the conceptual circular photovoltaic model is capable of providing Supportive strategical recommendations for industry policy makers besides being descriptive (Wambach, et al., 2024). Through this, logical progression, transparency and reproducibility can be passed from the academic documents to recommendations.

3.6 Limitations of the methodology

With the secondary nature of these available details, limitations that came attached with them have to be considered. Based on the boundary and quality of the academic documents, the standard of findings depends. Even though the chosen documents are very high in standard, there can be a gap between published details and latest achievements in the photovoltaic industry (Zobel, 2019) (ROSI, 2025) (PV Magazine, 2025).

Furthermore, with the secondary nature of the data available, factors such as policy impact, recovery rates and sustainability benchmarks remain almost similar to the original values of the used documents. However, with data remains similar to the original values, some difference may occur due to change in methodological approach, Geographical condition and assumptions done during the study (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Preet & Smith, 2024) (Franco & Groesser, 2021).

Also, even with the close similarities in the research documents, some challenges may occur due to lack of continuity and connectivity that remains within the documents. As an example, for a factor like ‘recovery efficiency’ one document may not include values for a certain material that other documents are mentioning, which creates difficulty in comparison (Deng, et al., 2019) (Ribo, et al., 2023).

When considering the conceptual framework that is mentioned here, it remains as an illustrative and analytical tool more than being a map for operations (Wambach, et al., 2024). No matter how much information is collected through various resources, it is not going to a level that testing in a field is applied. However, even with the above-mentioned limitations, the proposed methodology of this research is suitable for understanding strategic opportunities, trends and gaps in photovoltaic recycling Technology, while giving a strong starting point for future research.

4.1 Comparative analysis of recycling methods

When considering the comparative analysis, not only primary photovoltaic recycling approaches such as chemical, mechanical and thermal but also advanced hybrid processes like ROSI method are taken into account. With the help of available literature, analysis is done considering the factors such as Technology readiness level (TRL), environment impacts, process complexity, recovery efficiency and energy consumption.

4.1.1 Mechanical recycling

As the name suggests, this process is based on a physical separation method that proceeds with the help of factors such as size, material density and shape (Chen, et al., 2023) (Sark, et al., 2024). Dismantling, shredding and sorting are the main steps involved in the mechanical recycling process of photovoltaic components. To remove wiring harness, aluminum frames and junction boxes, methods of manual separation or an automated dismantling systems are used in the industrial level mechanical recycling systems (Zobel, 2019) (Preet & Smith, 2024). Under this process components such as junction boxes are dismantled to recover copper from internal conductors and aluminum frames are sent to the furnace to recover aluminum (Zobel, 2019) (Franco & Groesser, 2021). After that, laminated glass cell encapsulant composite is crushed using mills, so that manageable size pieces of the module can be obtained (Fan, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019). Furthermore, these module pieces go through a secondary milling process of vibrating screen or air classifier, so that pieces can be clarified and separated as rough or fine (Zobel, 2019) (OECD, 2016).

With technology readiness level of 8 to 9 values, mechanical recycling can be considered as the most common method in Europe that comes under waste electrical and electronic equipment directive. In this method, recovery rates of aluminum frames can reach up to 100% while rates for glass can reach around 95% (solar power europe, 2025) (Zobel, 2019) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). To recover metal Embedded in the laminate, eddy current separators of optical sorter are used in some advanced facilities. Some of the main disadvantages in this process are low percentage (less than 30%) of silicon wafer recovery and recovered glass cannot be used for high value application. This is happened mainly due to the

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higher bond between encapsulant and silicon wafer and with the use of large mechanical forces causes to wafer contamination and breakage. Therefore, that silicon usually downcycle to applications of meteorological Silicon or used as filler materials for non-electronic related products (Zobel, 2019) (Singh, et al., 2021). Even though, mechanical recycling process is energy efficient, the purity of the recovered material is considerably low. This low energy consumption is due to, most of the energy given is in mechanical form such as motors or conveyors (Chen, et al., 2023) (Franco & Groesser, 2021). Due to this energy efficiency, this method is highly economical to be done in higher quantities if the recovered materials such as glass can be used for other applications (solar power europe, 2025). When it comes to the photovoltaic industry, the mechanical recycling method is considered as a low efficient method, due to the inability to maintain a close loop photovoltaic life cycle (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (European Commission, 2025).

4.1.2 Thermal recycling

A high temperature process such as pyrolysis is used to separate the encapsulant layer, to free the material within, when performing thermal recycling (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024) (Fu, et al., 2018). To avoid oxidation of valuable components, in pyrolysis method, an environment without oxygen, is used (Fu, et al., 2018) (Zobel, 2019). Generally, this process may reach a temperature around 450 Celsius to 650 Celsius but in special cases, this may increase up to 700 Celsius where complete degradation of encapsulant may be achieved (Fan, et al., 2024). By overcoming difficulties in the previously mentioned mechanical recycling method, more successful separation of silicon wafer and metallic contacts is achieved using thermal recycling method.

In the thermal recycling process, first the modules are disassembled to remove junction boxes and Frames (Fan, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019). Then the modules are sent into the heating chamber with controlled temperature. Inside the heating chamber, the encapsulant goes through a thermal decomposition process to release solar cells and other materials inside (Chen, et al., 2023) (Zobel, 2019). Temperature of the heating chamber and the time of heating affects the grade of the silicon (Fan, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019) (Peng, et al., 2012). Excessive presence inside the heating chamber or maintaining high temperatures may cause micro cracks in the Silicon wafer resulting them to be useless for high grade applications after recycling (Zobel, 2019).

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Even with the technology readiness level of 6 to 8 values which indicate average to partially high industrial suitability, thermal recycling processes have been able to achieve a higher percentage of silicon recovery rate, which is around 80%, while displaying the capability to recover silver contacts (Zobel, 2019) (Australian PV Institute, 2023).

Disadvantages of this process can be mentioned as. requirement of highly regulated conditions to minimize hazardous byproducts and requirement of high amounts of energy (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022). Therefore, management of gaseous by-products can be identified as the important concern of thermal recycling (Fu, et al., 2018) (European Commission, 2025). Ethylene-Vinyl Acetate is the most commonly used encapsulant in photovoltaic modules and when it goes through thermal degradation it releases volatile organic compounds (VOCs) and toxic gases like Acetic Acid vapor (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022). To minimize these effects in an industrial scale operation, Effective off-gas treatment systems such as activated carbon filtration and catalytic oxidation are used.

4.1.3 Chemical recycling

The separation method of materials from the Encapsulant layer in the chemical recycling process is, dissolving with the help of acids or solvents (Chen, et al., 2023) (Wambach, et al., 2024). What makes chemical recycling method different from thermal or mechanical recycling method is it focuses on preserving chemical and physical quality of the valuable material such as silver contacts and silicon wafer, to reuse in photovoltaic module manufacturing, while enabling a photovoltaic life cycle (Sark, et al., 2024) (Chen, et al., 2023).

Similar to previously mentioned recycling processes, chemical recycling also begins with dismantling junction boxes and frames for pre-treatment (Zobel, 2019). There after photovoltaic modules are Submerged in a chemical solution of organic solvent such as dimethylformamide, trichloroethylene or acidic solution like Sodium Hydroxide or nitric acid (Chen, et al., 2023) (Wambach, et al., 2024). These two chemical solutions have two separate uses. For the purpose of dissolving ethylene-vinyl acetate, Organic solvent are used and to free silicon wafers by itching metallic layer, acidic solutions are used (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024). By removing anti-reflective coating and metallization layers without damaging the crystalline structure, hydrofluoric acid or potassium hydroxide like itching solutions helps to conduct the silicon recovery process (Wambach, et al., 2024). Because of this highly efficient

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method, silicon wafer can be reused in new solar cells to produce cells with almost the same solar efficiency (Wambach, et al., 2024). By leaching in nitric acid, silver in the front contacts can be extracted into silver nitrate, which can be taken into metallic silver after precipitation methods. The advantage of this method is that the recovery rate of silver, remains more than 95% (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Peng, et al., 2012).

Even though with the low technology readiness levels around 4 to 6 because of scalability challenges, chemical handling risks and high operational costs, Silicon recovery rate remains more than 95% while maintaining high quality that can be again used for manufacturing of silicon wafers (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019). However current market value of recovered materials remains less valuable than the cost of recycling process (regulatory compliant chemical procurement and disposal). Despite the cost inefficiency, the chemical recycling method has a high probability of achieving close loop photovoltaic manufacturing, due to the capability of recovering high quality silicon wafer and valuable metals such as silver (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025).

4.1.4 Hybrid and advanced recycling

Hybrid recycling process have been able to connect different steps of mechanical thermal and chemical recycling processes, while gaining advantages of each process and avoiding their weakness (Fan, et al., 2024) (Chen, et al., 2023) (Wambach, et al., 2024). Improving recovery yield and generating output with high purity levels are the main goals of the hybrid recycling method (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019). For the purpose of recovering a higher percentage of material while retaining the high purity level, hybrid processes such as the ‘Recycling of solar industry’(ROSI) method are used (ROSI, 2025) (Fan, et al., 2024). ROSI Method can be identified as a joint method including precision mechanical dismantling with thermal and chemical treatment.

As the first step of this process, junction boxes and frames are separated using the mechanical recycling method for direct recycling of copper and aluminum (Zobel, 2019). Then the laminated cell glass assembly is heated in a control environment to lose the encapsulant, so that silicon wafer can be separated without any thermal damage (ROSI, 2025) (Fan, et al., 2024). Immediately after, a mild chemical bathing process is done to reduce remaining encapsulant and metallization strips of the cells. Even though this process still remains under pilot facilities, a higher percentage of silicon recovery rates and more than 95% of silver

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recovery rate have been achieved through this process (ROSI, 2025) (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Hund, et al., 2020).

For the purpose of increasing the efficiency of the hybrid recycling systems, robotics and process control algorithms are commonly used (solar power europe, 2025) (Ribo, et al., 2023). Move over, there are systems that can identify damaged silicon wafer, so that they can be sent for the necessary repair and also there can be found some pilot programs that use close loop solvent recovery units and waste heat recovery systems that have been able to use sustainability methods to minimize operational costs (Zobel, 2019) (Ribo, et al., 2023) (Fu, et al., 2018) (Franco & Groesser, 2021). With the technology readiness level of 6 to 7, hybrid recycling systems are still not fully commercial systems (Zobel, 2019) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). Requirement of specially trained workers, high initial investment and the complexity of the process have been identified as several main reasons for this (Deng, et al., 2019) (OECD, 2016). However, to move towards a circular economy while achieving sustainable goals, the hybrid recycling system can be named as the most promising recycling method (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025).

In conclusion it is clear that, all the above mentioned recycling methods have their individual advantages and no method can provide a sustainable recovery method for all the components in a photovoltaic system (Zobel, 2019) (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Fu, et al., 2018). Mechanical recycling method is the most economical recycling method but when it comes to recovery of silicon for semiconductor reuse, it is not considered as a very efficient method (Chen, et al., 2023) (Zobel, 2019). The thermal recycling method is capable of recovering some amount of silicon and silver, however there can be some energy management problems (Fu, et al., 2018) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). Chemical recycling method can be identified as the most successful method of material recovery, but when it is performed on a large scale there is a risk of various environmental hazards (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Deng, et al., 2019). By mitigating all those limitations hybrid recycling method is introduced, however it still happens in a very controlled environment due to lack of industrial level adaptations (ROSI, 2025) (OECD, 2016). Therefore, according to the material recovery goal, regional policy frameworks and infrastructure availability, the most suitable recycling method has yet to be decided (European Commission, 2025). Therefore, throughout this analysis, the need of the multi-technological recycling industry is highlighted to move towards a sustainable photovoltaic life cycle (Biyouki, et al., 2024).

4.2 Sustainability performance

4.2.1 Energy payback time impacts by recycling method

Energy payback time of a photovoltaic system can be defined as the time that is required to generate an equal amount of energy that is spent to create the photovoltaic system, which is a crucial parameter to decide methods for end of life photovoltaic material recovery (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024). If a photovoltaic system is created using virgin materials, depending on the location of installation and levels of solar radiation, energy payback time can vary between 1 to 3 years (Fan, et al., 2024) (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). As the use of recycling material reduces consumption of energy, related to Silicon purification, metallization and raw material extractions, energy payback time can be reduced in a considerable amount (Chen, et al., 2023) (Singh, et al., 2021) (Peng, et al., 2012).

If the photovoltaic system is created with the use of mechanically recycled components, then the reduction of energy payback time is considerably low, as manufacturing of aluminum frames is not an energy intensive process (Zobel, 2019) (Franco & Groesser, 2021). As the recovered silicon using mechanical recycling process is not in high quality, they have less contribution to energy payback time of photovoltaic systems, however as it can be used for non-electronic related application, energy payback time can be reduced indirectly (Zobel, 2019).

When it comes to the thermal recycling method, energy payback time can be significantly reduced as the thermal method is able to recover Silicon wafer at a moderate level. In optimum conditions, with control paralysis processes, Silicon wafer recovery rate can be reached more than 70% and therefore, energy payback time can be reduced in few months (Zobel, 2019) (Fan, et al., 2024). However, as the thermal recycling method is a highly energy intensive process, the net energy benefits are limited (Fu, et al., 2018) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014).

With the chemical recycling process, near semiconductor grade purity silicon can be recovered in 95% recovery rate and therefore it has been identified as one of the best methods to reduce energy payback time (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Peng, et al., 2012). Due to the high quality of the recovered silicon wafer, it can be directly sent to the photovoltaic manufacturing process and nearly 30% of photovoltaic life cycle energy can be reduced (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (Wambach, et al., 2024). However, to remain these benefits, a system with the capability

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of handling environmental impacts with the consumption of a low amount of energy has to be maintained (Fu, et al., 2018) (Deng, et al., 2019).

Even though the hybrid recycling system is still in operation under pilot facilities, it is capable of performing material recovery while consuming a low amount of energy and this leads to significant reduction in energy payback time. According to research done in a pilot plant, hybrid recycling systems have been able to achieve nearly 20% reduction of energy payback time, providing evidence of significant potential towards future improvements (ROSI, 2025) (Wambach, et al., 2024).

4.2.2 Greenhouse gas emission reduction potential

Operations such as module assembly, fabrication of wafers, purification of silicon and processing of cells are the main causes for Greenhouse gas emission, in photovoltaic industry (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024). With the involvement of large amounts of heat and electricity inputs, according to the processing parameters of the energy, a considerable amount of carbon dioxide equivalent emissions can occur (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022). However, by applying end of life recycling method into the photovoltaic industry, greenhouse gas emissions can be reduced as it minimizes the production of virgin material (Fu, et al., 2018) (Franco & Groesser, 2021).

Figure 4.1 Carbon emissions by scenario

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When it comes to mechanical recycling, it reduces the greenhouse gas emission by rescuing aluminum frame and junction boxer from all photovoltaic modules. By reusing aluminum frames, almost 95% of virgin aluminum production related emissions can be reduced (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). When it comes to thermal recycling method, it can further reduce Greenhouse gas emissions compared to mechanical recycling, as it is able to recover silver and silicon from end-of-life photovoltaic modules (Zobel, 2019). However, to achieve this reduction in greenhouse gas emission through thermal recycling process, appropriate process control methods have to be used. With the use of waste heat integration methods and generation of electricity using Renewable Sources, can mitigate these limitations (Fu, et al., 2018) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). Even though the thermal recycling process can recover silicon and silver, chemical recycling method is the recycling method that is able to reduce Greenhouse gas emission in highest percentages, due to its capability of recovering materials without any structural damage so that they can be directly implemented into the manufacturing process. With proper safety procedures of chemical handling, processing of low carbon energy and effective solvent recovery, around 30% of greenhouse gas emission can be reduced through chemical recycling process as it avoids virgin production of polysilicon materials (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (Wambach, et al., 2024). Compared to all those recycling methods, hybrid recycling process can have the advantages of each process to recover each material in the highest percentage while reducing Greenhouse gas emission (ROSI, 2025) (Fu, et al., 2018).

4.2.3 Contribution to circular economy goals.

Preserving the value of materials, minimization of waste and longevity of product life cycle are the main objectives of the circular economy framework (European Commission, 2021). When considering photovoltaic systems, to achieve the above mentioned goals, end of life cycle practices plays a major role by sending recycled materials to the manufacturing process while minimizing the use of virgin material (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025).

In the mechanical recycling method, by sending recovered material such as aluminum frames and glass directly to the photovoltaic manufacturing process, the circular economy goals were achieved. Even though the recovered glass in mechanical recycling process is not in solar grade, by sending them to non-electronic related manufacturing processes, a considerable amount of circularity has been achieved (Zobel, 2019). In the thermal recycling process with the partial recovery of silicon wafer and silver like valuable material, circular economy goals

Sustainability and Recycling Pathways in Photovoltaic Energy Systems were achieved. By maintaining higher levels of material functionality according to the circular economy principles, these recovered silicon wafers and silver can be successfully reused in the Photovoltaic manufacturing process (Wambach, et al., 2024). With the chemical recycling process, it is much easier to recover solar grade silicon wafer and high value materials such as silver, while enabling the close loop photovoltaic manufacturing process and therefore higher levels of circularity can be achieved with reduction of virgin material use (Wambach, et al., 2024). Even though the hybrid recycling process still remains under pilot plants, as it uses various recycling techniques to achieve higher levels of material recovery rates and quality, with combination of directives such as design for recycling principles and extended producer responsibility, it has potential to achieve greater circular economy and sustainability goals (European Commission, 2021) (solar power europe, 2025) (OECD, 2016).

4.3 Conceptual model for circular photovoltaic deployment

For Purpose integration of efficient end of life processing, sustainable designs and reintegration of materials, into a closed loop value chain, circular photovoltaic model work as a strong structure. While analyzing policy and technical challenges that are present today, the conceptual circular economy model has been given several solutions based on reviewed literature (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025).

4.3.1 Input and limitations of the system

With the circular economy conceptual model, all the stages of the photovoltaic life cycle such as material extraction, manufacturing process, installation, operation and end of life recycling have been properly analyzed, so that it is possible to suggest options for re-inclusion of recycled materials. Inside the conceptual model, the sources of inputs have been categorized into three main parts as primary resources, secondary resources and auxiliary inputs. Under primary sources all the virgin materials are categorized and for the secondary resources, recovered materials from the recycling process have been included and auxiliary inputs are described as inputs such as water, necessary Chemicals and energy. The main focus of the conceptual model is to increase the use of secondary resources while reducing the consumption of primary resources and auxiliary inputs to minimize the financial and environmental footprint (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007) (Hund, et al., 2020).

4.3.2 Implementation of design for recycling

Basics of design for recycling (DFR) such as junction boxes that can easily separate and encapsulant consisting reversible adhesion properties have been embodied in the manufacturing step. With the basics of designed for recycling, efficiency of the recovery in mechanical and hybrid recycling methods can be increased without any follow up process (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025). Moreover, with inclusion of product passports such as maintaining digital records related to instructions for recycling and the composition of the materials, helps to increase the efficiency of recovery process (European Commission, 2025).

4.3.3 Optimizing the recycling method

When considering the Optimization methods, the end-of-life stage has to be created as a template that decides the most suitable recycling method out of mechanical, thermal, chemical and hybrid method, depending on the used technology, recovery goals and physical condition of the photovoltaic modules. To improve this further, machine learning and artificial intelligent based sorting methods can be used (Ribo, et al., 2023) (solar power europe, 2025).

4.3.4 Circularity methods of materials

Recycle materials are directed into specific circularity stages such as, aluminum and glass are sent to secondary manufacturing and high value materials like silver and silicon wafer which are recovered in near perfect conditions are redirected to the photovoltaic manufacturing process. To ensure the circularity of the process without a need of any outside involvement or additional resources, practices such as maintaining regional reprocessing plants, managing timely supply chain and minimizing emissions that happened during transportation, are used (Zobel, 2019) (Fan, et al., 2024) (Wambach, et al., 2024).

4.3.5 Connection between strategies and industry demands

Photovoltaic industry related directives and market techniques such as mandate related to recycled materials, extended producer responsibility (EPR) and recycling plants, are included in the conceptual framework of the circular economy. These directives motivate photovoltaic

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manufacturers to absorb various designs for recycling (DFR) techniques and to increase recycling, quantitatively. Furthermore, with standardization methods related to performance and origin, trust of the interested parties were uplifted and therefore industrial demand for recycled photovoltaic material has been increased (European Commission, 2021) (OECD, 2016) (solar power europe, 2025).

4.3.6 Constant growth and sustainability response

In this circular economy conceptual framework, life cycle assessment is included as a feedback loop so that parameters such as recovery efficiency, energy payback time and greenhouse gas emissions, can be analyze as soon as they are recorded. Through this, continuous development of recycling and manufacturing processes can be done, while updating the system according to the changing industrial demands and new technologies (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Franco & Groesser, 2021).

In conclusion, the proposed conceptual model has been able to overcome technological barriers that are present in the available recycling methods while matching them with policy framework, so that it can lead to a completely circular photovoltaic industry (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (solar power europe, 2025) (European Commission, 2025).

5.1 Interpretation of results

When considering the recycling methods shown in the result section, it has been clear that none of the recycling methods is individually capable of achieving the circularity in photovoltaic life cycle.

Even though when comparing the maturity, mechanical recycling method stands High, it is only capable of recovering bulk materials such as aluminum while providing a minimum level contribution towards the circularity in photovoltaic industry (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Masson, et al., 2023). Even with the already available advantages such as low energy consumption, strong infrastructure availability and scalability, mechanical recycling method is unable to achieve circularity due to inability of recovering high purity silicon wafer or silver which affects the greenhouse gas emission and energy payback time of the photovoltaic life cycle (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Australian government, 2025).

While improving the recovery quality and energy payback time, thermal recycling method have been able to dissolve encapsulant layer and release silicon wafer and silver in a considerably good condition (Chen, et al., 2023) (solar power europe, 2025) (ROSI, 2025). But as the name suggest, thermal recycling method involved with high temperature processing and energy demand, therefore it is required to maintain necessary 'off gas treatment' and process management techniques to avoid environmental hazards (Fu, et al., 2018) (NREL, 2025). Therefore it is clear that thermal recycling method have overcome some challenges that are present in mechanical recycling method, however the scalability of thermal recycling is present due to the requirement of high level of energy and environment hazard management techniques (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

Even under the experimentation level, chemical recycling method have been able to reach almost perfect sustainable and circular photovoltaic life cycle, by recovering silicon wafer and silver in high purity levels (Singh, et al., 2021) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022) (OECD, 2016). However in an industrial level applications, it has a low level of technology readiness levels due to chemical handling risks, higher operating costs and reagent recovery boundaries (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Preet & Smith, 2024).

Hybrid recycling systems can be considered as a strategic combination of mechanical recycling systems to recover bulk materials with thermal and chemical recycling methods to

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recover high value materials such as Silicon wafer and silver in a high purity condition (Fan, et al., 2024) (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (nature, 2025). Objectives of circular economy such as material purity, adaptability of the process and high levels of recovery yields have been able to achieved through hybrid recycling system (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Deng, et al., 2019). According to the research of pilot facilities, with the help of efficient management of resources and integration of renewable energy, hybrid recycling methods can achieve equality between economic feasibility and sustainable performance (PV Magazine, 2025).

It is clear that to achieve circularity in photovoltaic industry, combination of suitable recycling methods for each material is required, apart from following single recycling method. When directing towards proper industrial adaptation, policy guidelines like economic incentive and extended producer responsibility is essential. Moreover, with the improvement in design for recycling principles, subsequent processing difficulties can be reduced (Hund, et al., 2020) (European Commission, 2025) (Science, 2025). According to the circular economy Framework suggested in the methodology section, these objectives can be achieved while providing a considerable amount of sustainability while maintaining economic benefits (Peng, et al., 2012).

5.2 Limitation in high value recycling

Even with the high level of sustainability and economic advantages present in the photovoltaic recycling, various limitations such as operation and technical, affect the deployment of industrial scale processes. When considering the technical limitation, the strong bond between glass and silicon wafer through the encapsulant layer, is an obstacle to recover high value material such as silicon wafer without any damage (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Weckend, et al., 2016). With mechanical recycling method it is nearly impossible to separate silicon wafer without any damage, however with necessary controlling methods thermal and chemical recycling methods are able to recover these materials with minimum damage (Chen, et al., 2023) (ROSI, 2025) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022).

When it comes to operational limitations, unavailability of standardized design for photovoltaic modules have been identified as an issue, because due to that, a variety of techniques and materials are used for encapsulant and methods of interconnection (Masson, et al., 2023) (solar power europe, 2025). This will increase the operational cost with the requirement of maintaining an adaptable recycling process. Furthermore, due to lack of availability of worldwide large-scale photovoltaic waste, stakeholders have been discouraged

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from investing in construction of sophisticated industrial level recycling plants and it will take nearly the end of 2020 decade to receive a considerable amount of end of life photovoltaic modules (European Commission, 2021) (Australian government, 2025) (NREL, 2025).

Figure 5.1 Photovoltaic waste projection in Australia

As harmful reagents and gases have to be controlled with strong recovery, containment and neutralization systems, workplace and environmental safety is considered as a major concern regarding chemical recycling (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022) (Preet & Smith, 2024). Moreover, the thermal recycling process needs an emission controlling system to detain toxic by-products and unstable organic compounds that releases with the decomposition of encapsulants (Fu, et al., 2018) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

When considering the directives and industrial demands, lack of regulatory pressure have been identified as a main boundary. Even though the countries in Europe remain under WEEE directive, most of the countries in the world do not have necessary end of life photovoltaic module recycling management directives (Hund, et al., 2020) (European Commission, 2025). Without necessary directives and government incentives, photovoltaic module manufacturers have very limited interest in moving towards sophisticated recycling and recovery methods, while mechanical recycling which meets minimum Recycling limit can be performed in an economical manner (Science, 2025).

5.3 Circular design options

In improving the efficiency of material recovery and simplicity of the recycling process, Circularity of the photovoltaic system is helpful (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024). For the purpose of increasing the operation time period, reducing toxicity and simple disassembling of the precious material and parts, photovoltaic module manufacturers have been focused on implementing design for recycling (DFR) practices into manufacturing steps. One of the areas of interest that comes under definition for recycling is, use of reversible encapsulants. When recycling, there is no need of intense heat or highly corrosive chemicals for separating silicon wafer from glass, as this reversible encapsulant can be dissolved with specific conditions (Chen, et al., 2023) (ROSI, 2025).

To minimize the changes that makes recycling difficult, bringing certain measurements and benchmarks to ways of interconnection, material mixture and measurement of the photovoltaic module are important (Masson, et al., 2023) (Weckend, et al., 2016). By aligning all the designs into a predefined set of measurements, the recycling industry can easily go through their process with higher rate of efficiency as recycling facilities don't have to do the recycling process according to various number of module designs (European Commission, 2021) (solar power europe, 2025). Also with including parts such as glass covers and junction boxer as separately changeable components, capability to repair the photovoltaic module can be increased, rather than replacing the complete photovoltaic module (Fan, et al., 2024) (Zobel, 2019).

With technological advancement, it has been able to store comprehensive information on methods of photovoltaic connection, material ratio and optimum method for recycling and this is called 'product passport' (Hund, et al., 2020) (Ribo, et al., 2023). This information is greatly helpful to recycling plant workers to arrange their work more efficiently. Also, if strength of the photovoltaic module can be maintained, then by using lightweight module designs, various costs can be reduced such as material, transportation and recycling (Australian government, 2025) (Australian PV Institute, 2023). These options can be combined with effective end of life policies, so that close loop photovoltaic industry can be achieved.

5.4 Synchronizing available policies to present industry

It has been a clear fact that currently available policies related to the photovoltaic industry are not sufficient to enable high value recycling (Hund, et al., 2020) (European Commission, 2025). Extended producer responsibility (EPR) can be identified as, currently available most up to date policy that is active under European WEEE rules. Through addressing accountability of the photovoltaic module manufacturers, towards assisting economically on recovery of end of life photovoltaic modules, this policy motivates practices such as design for recycling (Ribo, et al., 2023) (Science, 2025). By spreading these practices on an international level, a solid foundation can be laid towards sustainable and circular photovoltaic implementations (Peng, et al., 2012).

To direct secondary material properly into photovoltaic module production lines, introducing regulation and standards related to targeted recycling goals is necessary (OECD, 2016) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). As an example, mandating a specific percentage of recycled material such as aluminum to be used in a newly produced photovoltaic modules, will increase the requirement for development in recycling and decrease the use of virgin materials (nature, 2025) (Wambach, et al., 2024). However, these rules must be implemented with some quality control methods to minimize the suspicion that lies within the manufacturers regarding the quality (Deng, et al., 2019).

For the purpose of industrial level implementations, financial support through government or organizations is needed in sectors such as Infrastructure for recycling, manufacturers who are adapting circular principles and researchers who are working on laws impact recycling (PV Magazine, 2025) (European Commission, 2025). Simultaneously, by implementing fines for avoiding practices related to recycling, may lead to manufacturers to consider recycling as a financially beneficial decision (Hund, et al., 2020) (Science, 2025). Furthermore, absorbing technological developments that are happening around the world related to recycling and manufacturing designs of photovoltaic modules is crucial to overcome existing boundaries in the industry (Peng, et al., 2012). By maintaining a database related to material recovery parameters, Quantitative details on annual end of life photovoltaic modules and percentage of worldwide deployment of photovoltaic technology, is helpful to create policies and to assist developing countries to absorb the new technologies related to photovoltaic systems, effectively (Science, 2025).

5.5 Technological boundaries

Even with higher benefits in photovoltaic technology still there are major limitations present in the environmental, economical and technical sector (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Masson, et al., 2023). When it comes to financially beneficial recycling processes like mechanical recycling, there are limitations in recovering precious materials such as silver and silicon on an industrial scale (Weckend, et al., 2016) (Australian government, 2025). Moreover the recovered glass is low quality, so that it has to be used for implementations such as construction aggregates and therefore circularity of a photovoltaic system is degraded (European Commission, 2021) (solar power europe, 2025).

In the thermal recycling method, it can recover high value material in a considerable quality, but the energy use in this process is high (ROSI, 2025) (NREL, 2025). To perform processes such as pyrolysis requires around 500 to 600 Celsius of temperature and if the energy generated for this process is done using fossil fuel, then an additional harm to the environment will be done (Fu, et al., 2018) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007). Additionally, if the encapsulant decomposing process is done without proper containment of the emission, then expensive gas treatment systems have to be used to prevent toxic gases from releasing to the environment and this will reduce the financial benefits (Australian PV Institute, 2023) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007).

The chemical recycling process is able to recover precious materials in very high purity percentages, but it generates several safety and scalability problems (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022) (OECD, 2016) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). Due to the application of high quantities of chemicals, concerns related to operational cost, management of chemical waste and safety of the workers have been raised (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). Even though recovery of nearly 95% of silicon from the module is achievable through the chemical recycling process, it still has been a challenge to overcome financial and safety limitations (Franco & Groesser, 2021) (nature, 2025).

Even under the experimental stage, the hybrid recycling process is the only method that have been able to avoid most of the limitations related to recycling while obtaining combined advantages of all the recycling processes (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Deng, et al., 2019). However, as the hybrid recycling process is still in the experimental stage, the lack of details on economic benefits raises several concerns related to optimization of the process, reliability in long term and feasibility (PV Magazine, 2025).

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Apart from technological limitations, lack of international standards for module design, have been a crucial fact that complicates recycling (Masson, et al., 2023) (Weckend, et al., 2016). Also, the different types of interconnections, combination of materials and encapsulants complicates the recycling process while minimizing the financial benefits (European Commission, 2021) (Australian government, 2025). Furthermore, the lack of considerable quantity of end of life photovoltaic modules make it difficult to increase the infrastructure capacity of the available recycling plant as this minimize motivation towards financial investments (European Commission, 2025) (Science, 2025).

In conclusion, even the individual recycling methods have certain benefits, none of them have been able to reach economical scalability, purity of material, environment safety and high recovery yield all together (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Masson, et al., 2023) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022). To match the difference between the financial reality, research and development, inefficiencies in policy support, collected industrial actions and innovation have to be mitigated (Hund, et al., 2020) (Peng, et al., 2012).

6 CONCLUSION

The continuous development of photovoltaic Technology related applications have highlighted the importance of maintaining the sustainability of energy and effective end of life management practices (Sark, et al., 2024) (Chen, et al., 2023) (Singh, et al., 2021). The main focus of this thesis has been, to evaluate the recycling pathways and sustainability of photovoltaic systems, while analyzing the performance of presently available recycling Technologies, adherence to sustainability matrix and implementations with in circular economy framework (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024) (Masson, et al., 2023). Through gathering various perceptions from analysis of policies, studies related to life cycle assessment and academic publications related to technical details, this research gives strong analysis on the pathways to move from linearity towards circularity and resource efficient life cycle (Weckend, et al., 2016) (European Commission, 2021) (Australian government, 2025).

The presently available literature proves that mechanical recycling method is the most technologically seasoned recycling method, but the benefits are limited to recovery of bulk materials, minimizing greenhouse gases and slightly reducing energy payback time (Sark, et al., 2024) (Masson, et al., 2023) (Weckend, et al., 2016). When it comes to the thermal recycling method, it has been able to recover precious material like silicon wafer and silver, however it is not considered as the most efficient method of recycling, because it comes with some limitations such as energy intensity of the process and requirement of environmental safety and control methods (ROSI, 2025) (NREL, 2025). Chemical recycling is considered as the most suitable method for recovering solar grade silicon and silver, but this method has some limitations such as challenges related to chemical handling, problems in scalability and minimum levels of technology readiness (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022) (OECD, 2016) (Preet & Smith, 2024). As all above mentioned methods have their own limitations, hybrid recycling method have been introduced to collect the strengths of each method while avoiding weaknesses, however this method requires further technological and financial improvements because this recycling method still remains under laboratory testing level (Wambach, et al., 2024) (Deng, et al., 2019).

In the point of view of sustainability, adapting recycling technologies into photovoltaic systems has been helpful in minimizing problems related to air pollution and energy spent inside the life cycle (OECD, 2016) (nature, 2025). Moreover, out of all the recycling methods chemical and hybrid recycling have been identified as two Methods that can achieve the highest

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amount of advantages (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Fan, et al., 2024) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). Primarily these two recycling methods help to maintain circularity by recovering precious materials and sending them back to the photovoltaic module manufacturing process. Through this, consumption of virgin resources and photovoltaic waste that end up in landfills get reduced. With the help of suggested conceptual model, supportive policy frameworks, design for recycling basics and loops of material integration can be joined together to generate a circular and sustainable photovoltaic industry (Hund, et al., 2020) (Peng, et al., 2012).

Even with various achievements are present in the photovoltaic industry, there are still some limitations that exist (ROSI, 2025) (United Nations Environment Programme, 2007) (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, 2022). In technological perspective toxic waste handling, scalability of the process and delamination of the Silicon wafer have been identified as troublesome. From the angle of marketing, lack of industrial scale recycling facilities, ambiguity in market for recycled solar grade materials and shortage in end of life photovoltaic modules have been considered as problems (OECD, 2016) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014). Countries that are outside of the European Union have a limited number of policies to mandate circular end of life photovoltaic module practices and necessary financial intensives to promote them, therefore it is difficult to create positive arguments towards high value recycling (Hund, et al., 2020) (European Commission, 2025) (Science, 2025).

However, there are various new possibilities available to increase the progress of recycling. Integrating characteristics of circular design into photovoltaic modules like modular architectures and reversible encapsulants will make future recycling easier (Chen, et al., 2023) (Fan, et al., 2024) (Masson, et al., 2023). Directive measures such as extended producer responsibility, recycled content mandate and financial support will increase the absorption of recycling technology into module manufacturing (Hund, et al., 2020) (Ribo, et al., 2023) (Science, 2025). By synchronizing global standards and policies related to photovoltaic recycling methods, expanding of the sustainable and circular economy can be done (Peng, et al., 2012).

Overall, it is clear that, for a circular and sustainable photovoltaic technology, a complex and interconnected approach is needed rather than isolated technologies or policies (Sark, et al., 2024) (Biyouki, et al., 2024) (Wambach, et al., 2024). For the purpose of reaching a low carbon and resource efficient solar industry, it is essential to develop regulatory frameworks, embedding circular economy principles in to manufacturing process and improvements of recycling technology (Fan, et al., 2024) (Weckend, et al., 2016) (nature, 2025). Even though

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the present technology level of circularity is not very advanced, the path that the industry is following shows promising results towards a far more sustainable future (OECD, 2016) (Gerbinet, et al., 2014) (Peng, et al., 2012). Through this research, it has been able to gather available technologies, limitations and propose a futuristic model to help in future policy making and research. Finally, moving towards sustainable End of life photovoltaic systems is not just a pathway to secure the environmental hazards, it is also a crucial step in reserving precious materials that are necessary for the transition of Clean Energy.

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8.1 Graphviz code

```

digraph CircularPVModel {
    rankdir=TB;          /* top-to-bottom for A4 portrait */
    splines=ortho;
    nodesep=0.6;
    ranksep=0.9;
    fontsize=12;

    node [shape=box, style="rounded, filled", fillcolor=lightgrey, fontsize=11, width=3.2,
height=0.9];

    /* ----- Input layer ----- */
    subgraph cluster_inputs {
        label="Inputs";
        fontsize=13;
        style=dashed;
        color=gray;

        Primary [label="Primary Resources\n(Virgin Si, Ag, Al, Glass)"];
        Secondary [label="Secondary Resources\n(Recycled stock)"];
        Auxiliary [label="Auxiliary Inputs\n(Energy, Water, Chemicals)"];
    }

    /* ----- Lifecycle ----- */
    Raw [label="Raw Material Acquisition"];
    Manufacturing [label="Module Manufacturing\n(+ Design-for-Recycling,\nProduct
Passports)"];
    Installation [label="System Installation"];
    Operation [label="Operational Use\n(25–30 yrs; EPBT, EROI)"];
    EoL [label="End-of-Life Management\n(Disposal & Recycling)"];

```

Sustainability and Recycling Pathways in Photovoltaic Energy Systems

```
/* ----- Recycling cluster ----- */
subgraph cluster_recycling {
  label="Recycling Pathways";
  fontsize=13;
  style=dashed;
  color=blue;

  Mech [label="Mechanical Recycling"];
  Thermal [label="Thermal Recycling"];
  Chemical[label="Chemical Recycling"];
  Hybrid [label="Hybrid/Advanced Recycling"];
}

Reintegration [label="Material Reintegration\n(Recovered Si, Ag, Glass, Al)"];

/* ----- Policy & Feedback ----- */
Policy [label="Policy & Market Linkages\n(EPR, mandates, incentives, certification)"];
Feedback [label="Sustainability Feedback\n(LCA: EPBT, GHG, Recovery)"];

/* ----- Core connections ----- */
Primary -> Raw [penwidth=1.5];
Raw -> Manufacturing [label="Virgin input"];
Auxiliary -> Manufacturing [label="Energy/chemicals"];

Manufacturing -> Installation -> Operation -> EoL;

/* EoL branching into recycling methods */
EoL -> Mech [label="Modules"];
EoL -> Thermal [label="Modules"];
EoL -> Chemical [label="Modules"];
EoL -> Hybrid [label="Modules"];
```

Sustainability and Recycling Pathways in Photovoltaic Energy Systems

```
/* Recycling -> reintegration -> secondary -> manufacturing */
```

```
Mech -> Reintegration [label="Glass, Al (bulk)"];
```

```
Thermal -> Reintegration [label="Silicon, metals"];
```

```
Chemical -> Reintegration [label="High-purity Si, Ag"];
```

```
Hybrid -> Reintegration [label="Optimised recovery"];
```

```
Reintegration -> Secondary [label="Recovered stock"];
```

```
Secondary -> Manufacturing [label="Recycled input"];
```

```
/* Direct circular (highlighted) */
```

```
Reintegration -> Manufacturing [label="Circular flow", color=green, fontcolor=green,  
penwidth=2];
```

```
/* ----- Policy links ----- */
```

```
Policy -> Manufacturing [label="Eco-design standards", color=blue, penwidth=2];
```

```
Policy -> EoL [label="Regulation", color=blue, penwidth=2];
```

```
Policy -> Reintegration [label="Market incentives", color=blue, penwidth=2];
```

```
EoL -> Policy [label="Reporting/compliance", color=blue, penwidth=1.5];
```

```
/* ----- Sustainability feedback loop ----- */
```

```
Operation -> Feedback [style=dotted, label="Performance data"];
```

```
Reintegration -> Feedback [style=dotted, label="Recovery efficiency"];
```

```
Feedback -> Manufacturing [label="LCA-driven design", color=orange, penwidth=2];
```

```
Feedback -> EoL [label="Process optimisation", color=orange, penwidth=2];
```

```
Feedback -> Reintegration [label="Recovery targets", color=orange, penwidth=2];
```

```
/* Keep recycling methods aligned horizontally */
```

```
{rank=same; Mech; Thermal; Chemical; Hybrid;}
```

```
}
```

8.2 Gantt chart (2024/2025)

	Task 1	Task 2	Task 3	Task 4	Task 5
	Selecting a topic	Reading necessary academic publications and books	Creating thesis structure	Writing the thesis	Proof reading
October					
November					
December					
January					
February					
March					
April					
May					
June					
July					

Figure 8.1 Gantt chart